

WHY SENSORY SPACE DESIGN IS SO IMPORTANT?

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Universal Design (UD), coined by Ronald Mace (b.1941–d.1998), who is an architect by profession, to describe the concept of designing all products, buildings, environments, and/or services (PBES) to be aesthetic and usable to the greatest extent possible by all people, regardless of age, gender, race, belief, ability, physique, or socio-economic status. The concept of UD came about from an earlier concept of barrier-free accessibility for people with disabilities based on the pioneering work of Selwyn Goldsmith (b.1932–d.2011) on designing for the disabled (Goldsmith, 1963). Today, adaptive and assistive technology is also included to blend aesthetics into the UD.

There are seven UD guiding principles expounded by the Center for Universal Design (CUD) at the University of North Carolina (CUD, 1997) to be followed when designing a product, building, environment, and/or service (PBES):

1. Equitable use: The design of a PBES should be useful and/or marketable to a wide range of people with different degrees of varied abilities.
2. Flexibility in use: The design of a PBES should accommodate a wide range of individual preferential styles, likings, and abilities.
3. Simplicity and intuitiveness: The application in the design of a PBES should make it easy to understand and use without the need to consider a user's experience, knowledge, language skills, or current level of attention/concentration.
4. Perceptible information: The design of a PBES should communicate necessary information effectively to any user, regardless of his/her ambient conditions or sensory abilities.
5. Tolerance for error: The design of a PBES should minimize any possible form of hazards and/or adverse consequences of accidental or unintended actions.
6. Low physical and/or mental effort: The design of a PBES can be used efficiently and comfortably and with a minimum of physical and/or mental fatigue.; and
7. Size and space for approach and/or use: An appropriate size and space must be considered when using a PBES in terms of its approach, reach, manipulation, and use regardless of a user's body size, posture, or mobility.

These guiding principles are broader than those of accessible design and barrier-free design. They are succinctly defined with several brief guidelines (see CUD, 1997, for more detail) that can be applied to design processes in any of the following

three realms: physical, digital, or sensory. The sensory realm is our addition and it is this realm that we shall be focusing on in this article.

Sensory Experiences: Exteroceptive and Interoceptive Senses

Our world is full of sensory stimuli (e.g., noise, odor, glaring light) and also within each and every one of us (e.g., hyper-sensitivity and hypo-sensitivity to different sensory stimuli). Hence, we cannot ignore the importance of the sensory realm. Its impact on the way we orientate, adapt, or adjust ourselves in any sensory space and more so when our various sensory receptive fields are constantly being bombarded with so much sensory information.

Our human brain has a unique design that produces and modulates reactions and/or responses to our sensory experiences around us. These sensory experiences involve both exteroceptive senses (i.e., see-visual, hear/speak-auditory, touch-haptic, smell-olfactory, taste/eat-gustatory) and interoceptive senses (i.e., balance/move-vestibular/proprioceptive). The interface between the brain (and its nervous system and sub-systems) and the behavior (responses or reactions) as well as the environmental stimuli constitutes the sensory space, where sensory integration takes place.

For most of us, sensory integration or processing is generally overlooked in our daily experience. However, for someone with an intellectual and/or developmental disorder, the way the brain processes these sensory experiences can cause distress or discomfort. In some cases, the brain may become over-/under-responsive to some of these sensory stimuli. At other times, it may be unresponsive and hence does not react enough to a stimulus. Our sensory experiences often go beyond the five basic exteroceptive senses and can also negatively stimulate some deeper or interoceptive sensory senses, i.e., the tactile, vestibular, and proprioceptive.

Figure 1. Sensory Space

The Implicit Sensory Space

The first sensory space, i.e., internal/implicit, involves the autonomous nervous system (ANS) that controls and regulates the internal organs without any conscious recognition or effort by an individual. It consists of two nervous subsystems (NS): (i) sympathetic (SNS) and (ii) parasympathetic (PSNS). There is also the enteric nervous system (ENS) – also known as the intrinsic nervous system – which constitutes one of the main divisions of the ANS, and it consists of a mesh-like network of neurons that governs the function of the gastrointestinal tract (Furness, 2006). The ENS can function independently of the SNS and PSNS, although it may be influenced by them. As a result, the ENS is often regarded as the second brain (Dorland, 2012; Pocock & Richards, 2006). However, in this article, the ENS does not come into our discussion.

Figure 2. Internal/Implicit Sensory Space

The SNS is the fight-freeze-or-flight response of the NS, i.e., the way our body reacts to stress or danger, for instance. When the SNS is stimulated, several changes take place, e.g., heartbeat increases, pupils in the eyes dilate, muscles contract, production of saliva decreases, and bronchial tubes in the lungs dilate. This happens when an individual feels stressed or anxious, his heartbeat increases, the blood flow to the muscles also increases and the blood flow from his skin decreases. This involves involuntary unconscious activities that take place within the internal sensory space. The resultant sensory motor response or reaction can be resisting the source of stress or anxiety (fight response) or avoiding it altogether (flight response).

The PSNS is the rest-and-digest or feed-and-breed response (McCorry, 2007) of the NS, i.e., the way our body maintains a state of equilibrium. The PSNS response is accountable for regulating homeostasis, i.e., it restores an individual to a state of calmness and counterbalance in order for him/her to relax or recuperate. When the PSNS is stimulated, several specific responses are activated, e.g., saliva increases, heartbeat decreases, muscles relax, pupils in the eyes constrict, and urinary output increases. Hence, if we pat a dog/cat, soak ourselves in a hot bath, or get a good body massage, these are examples of PSNS-related activities.

Generally, both SNS and PSNS have opposing effects on an individual. That is to say, an increase in the activity of one system will see a simultaneous decrease in the activity of the other, resulting in very rapid and precise control of the individual's response/reaction. For instance, if a person feels threatened by an external source (e.g., a bully, tornado, or

grizzly bear), his/her SNS response of fight-freeze-flight (for survival's sake) would increase while the PSNS response of rest-and-digest or feed-and-breed (no time to rest or eat) would decrease.

Explicit Sensory Space

The second sensory space, i.e., external/explicit, involves the sensory-somatic nervous system (SSNS), also known as the voluntary nervous system, which constitutes a part of the peripheral nervous system. In this NS, external stimuli cause the voluntary movements of an individual. The SSNS consists of cranial and spinal nerves and contains the following neurons: (i) afferent sensory neurons, which transmit sensory information from the skin, skeletal muscle, and sensory organs to the central nervous system (CNS); and (ii) efferent motor neurons, which transmit messages about desired movement from the CNS to the muscles to make them contract (see Figure 3). Without the SSNS, an individual would not be able to process or register any incoming information about the environment (what s/he sees, feels, hears, smells, and/or tastes) and could not control his/her motor movements.

The SSNS is an important nervous system as it controls or regulates voluntary muscle movements and it is also associated with involuntary movements known as reflex arcs. During a reflex arc, muscles move involuntarily without input from the brain. It happens when a nerve pathway connects directly to the spinal cord. For example, if someone accidentally touches a boiling kettle, a reflex arc occurs almost immediately resulting in the jerking of one's hand back from the hot kettle.

In another example, imagine yourself out in a park for a leisure stroll one evening. While you are walking, you spot a black bear roaming in the park. You have read the news about an escaped bear from an animal sanctuary that morning. Your visual system (afferent sensory neurons) perceives the threat and relays the information to your brain, which also schema-matches with the news read earlier. Your brain then sends signals to engage your muscles (efferent motor neurons) to take action (motoric response). The SSNS activates your action to turn yourself (or your body) around and take a different route away from the beast, successfully avoiding the perceived threat and, hence, preventing a possible danger

Figure 3. External/Explicit Sensory Space

According to Ayres (1972), sensory integration (SI) is defined as "The neurological process that organizes sensation from one's own body and the environment and makes it possible to use the body effectively with the environment" (p.339).

However, for people with sensory processing challenges – often observed in those with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) – the way their brain processes these experiences can become a major source of distress and discomfort, resulting in anxiety, fear, and frustration. Hence, whatever happens in the outside or external sensory space can also affect the internal sensory space, and there are two key problems: (i) which exteroceptive and/or interoceptive senses are giving the problems; and (ii) how these senses misperceive (due to either commission or omission errors in the sensory processing) or dis-perceive (due to malfunctioning during the sensory processing) the incoming sensory stimuli. In other words, something is not working right or properly with the sensory nervous system due to some disturbance in either internal or external sensory space or both.

What does Sensory Space Design involve?

Technically speaking, as already mentioned earlier, the sensory space is an extent or expanse of a surface or three-dimensional area within which explicit and/or implicit stimuli are felt or processed, resulting in a particular sensory perception through the sensory experience. This sensory space can be formulated into a “design of space which, in turn, enriches shifting sensory environments” (Love, 2018, p.153). Love (2018) argued further that “Centrally recognized is that ‘reliable and unbiased knowledge about client requirements, along with user needs and behavior’” (p.153), is also essential to be taken into consideration in what we have termed the Sensory Space Design (SSD) if we want to maximize an individual’s optimal sensory performance. This, in turn, depends on the person’s Sensory Profile (see Dunn, 1999, for detail) and the seven guiding principles (not in order of priority) to create a suitable PBES (e.g., Sensory Room) that will meet the SSD criteria as follow:

Principle #1: Sensory equitability: Usable for anyone with varied sensory processing styles.

Principle #2: Sensory flexibility: Accommodable for different sensory processing styles.

Principle #3: Sensory perceptibility: Discernible by using different sensory receptors and processes.

Principle #4: Sensory preferentiality: Desirable form or choice of sensory processing style.

Principle #5: Sensory responsivity: Degree of activity (being hyper-, hypo-, or usual responsive) in terms of an action or effect to a sensory stimulus, and this is also known as the neurological threshold, i.e., how much of a sensory stimulus is required for one to respond (Dunn, 1999).

Principle #6: Sensory functionality: Degree of performance ability in terms of output provided by different responding or reacting senses.

Principle #7: Sensory proxemics: Use of space and the effects of the space on one’s behavior, communication, and social interaction. This includes the horizontal distance around a person as well as the vertical distance above and below him/her. This aspect constitutes one of the five sensory subcategories identified in nonverbal communication: haptics, kinesics, vocalics, and chronemics (Moore, 2010).

Among the seven guiding principles, sensory proxemics constitute the central premise that underlies the SSD. Without

it, there can be no sensory space. The term *proxemics* was first coined by Edward T. Hall (b.1914–d.2009), a cultural anthropologist, and is defined as the use of (social-physical) space as a specialized elaboration of culture (Hall, 1996). In other words, the distance surrounding a person forms a space. Hall (1996) divided this space/distance into four horizontal zones in terms of close and far phases: (1) intimate space; (2) personal space; (3) social space; and (4) public space. For the space within intimate distance and personal distance, it is called *personal space*. Next, the space within social distance and out of personal distance is referred to as *social space*. Lastly, the space within public distance is known as *public space*. This topic alone has much to offer and we shall discuss it as a separate article another time.

There is also vertical space/distance between an individual and his/her immediate surroundings. This vertical space/distance can be seen in two ways. First, in terms of physical space, it can refer to the height or the depth in relation to the person standing in that space. Next, in terms of social space, vertical space/distance conveys a certain degree of dominance or sub-ordination in an interpersonal relationship.

Conclusion

Today, the Sensory Room is making use of a ‘safe’ space to design a place for individuals with sensory issues to help them learn to cope with such challenges. It is hoped that it will ultimately help them learn to cope with seemingly normal sensory experiences.

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